

Design and Analysis of Hydro Jetting Nozzle

Chirag Gowda P¹, Rahul C Reddy¹, S Vishal¹, Dr. Nikhil Rangaswamy²

¹UG Students, School of Mechanical Engineering, REVA University, India

²Assistant Professor, School of Mechanical Engineering, REVA University, India

Abstract— *Hydrojet nozzles are crucial components in various applications ranging from industrial cleaning to propulsion systems. These nozzles utilize the power of high-pressure water jets to perform tasks efficiently and effectively. The design and functionality of hydrojet nozzles play a significant role in determining their performance and versatility. At the core of hydrojet nozzles is the principle of fluid dynamics, where pressurized water is accelerated through a small orifice to create a powerful jet. The shape and size of the orifice, as well as the internal geometry of the nozzle, are carefully engineered to achieve desired outcomes. Different types of hydrojet nozzles exist, including straight jet, fan jet, rotary jet, and pulsating jet nozzles, each suited for specific applications based on their unique characteristics. One of the key advantages of hydrojet nozzles is their ability to generate high-pressure streams of water, which can be tailored to suit various tasks. In industrial cleaning, hydro jet nozzles are employed to remove tough residues, coatings, and deposits from surfaces with precision and efficiency.*

Keywords— “Nozzle, Hydrojet, Design and Analysis”

I. INTRODUCTION

Hydrojet nozzles have emerged as a revolutionary solution for effectively clearing clogged drainage pipes, offering a powerful and efficient method to tackle stubborn blockages. These specialized nozzles utilize high-pressure water jets to dislodge and remove debris, sediment, and obstructions within pipes, ensuring a thorough and reliable cleaning process. In this context, the applications, materials employed in nozzle construction, and the requisite pressure requirements play pivotal roles in optimizing the performance of hydrojet systems. The effectiveness of hydrojet nozzles relies significantly on the materials used in their construction. Typically crafted from durable materials such as stainless steel, hardened alloys, or ceramics, these nozzles are designed to withstand the abrasive nature of the cleaning process. Stainless steel offers corrosion resistance, ensuring a prolonged lifespan and maintaining the nozzle's structural integrity even when subjected to high-pressure water jets and harsh cleaning environments.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW:

(1)Investigation of the flow phenomena in high-pressure water jet nozzles

Chemical Engineering Research And design

Volume165, Pages 320-332, January 2021, Oleg Urazmetov, Marcel Cadet, Roman Teutsch

- HPWJ nozzles are used in various applications including cleaning, cutting, deburring, and surface morphology modification. In the chemical industry, the pressure of HPWJ nozzles for cleaning is approximately 50 MPa. In mechanical engineering, HPWJ nozzles are used to transfer forces onto metallic or concrete materials, requiring higher operating pressures in the range of 100 MPa to 600 MPa. Different flow forms occur within the nozzle depending on the geometry of the HPWJ nozzle. Flow behavior in different shaped nozzles has been studied numerically and experimentally. Recent studies have shown that a sharp inlet edge in capillary nozzles is responsible for flow detachment. Wear of nozzles depends on the nozzle material, volume flow rate, and water hardness. The rounding of the inlet edge of a nozzle greatly influences the shape of the liquid jet. The ratio of nozzle length to nozzle diameter, known as l/d , influences the jet turbulence, jet breakup length, and the discharge coefficient. This paper presents a detailed numerical investigation of the flow in two nozzle types, focusing on the hydraulic-flip and cavitation phenomena. The study also aims to quantify wall shear stresses in the two nozzle types that cause or contribute to wear, especially in steel nozzles.

(2) Research on Flow Field Characteristics in Water Jet Nozzle and Surface Damage Caused by Target Impact**Ocean and Hydropower****25 July 2022, Qinghong Zhang, Zhouhao shi' Weidong Shi,**

- The study investigates the flow characteristics and failure characteristics of ultra-high-pressure gas-liquid jets in the range of 300 MPa. The jet atomization diffusion is attributed to friction between the liquid medium and the surrounding gas, mixed flow of broken water droplets, and cavitation. The jet diffusion process is essentially the energy exchange process between the jet in the core area and the turbulent flow in the atomization area. The water jet impacted the surface of the target to form a crater-like annular erosion pit. The central depression of the erosion area is caused by the damage of the material by the stagnation pressure in the core area. The flow characteristics of gas-liquid flow in the process of formation and diffusion in the high-pressure water jet nozzle are explored from the microscopic point of view, providing a theoretical basis for equipment optimization in engineering. The study is significant for the large-scale promotion and application of high-pressure water jet rust removal on the surface of ships.

(2) Experimental and numerical investigation of abrasive water jet nozzle Erosion**Powder Technology,****Volume 430, 1 December 2023, 119031, Chuanfu Shao, Zhaolong Ge, Zhe Zhou**

- Particle flow inside the nozzle is simulated using Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) method. Motion trajectories of incident particles are investigated through trajectory analysis. The erosion damage mechanism is analyzed by surface morphology and impact characteristics of the main abrasion region. Results show that particle impact position moves forward as the particle incident position moves away from the inlet centre. Sensitivity analyses show that erosion rate is most sensitive to pump pressure, impact frequency, impact velocity, and impact angle are most sensitive to particle size, pump pressure, and particle size. The erosion damage mechanism is micro-cutting due to the low angle impact of particles. The study's working condition is less than 20Mpa, ignoring the compressed volume of water.

(3) Study on Energy Conversion Efficiency and Structure Optimization of the Multi orifices Nozzle for Radial Jet Drilling**Geofluids,****Volume 2023 | Article ID 5517260 | 25 May 2023, Famu Huang, Ziheng Zhu, Jian Wang, Ping Zhang,**

- Underground gas storage (UGS) is crucial for mitigating seasonal fluctuations in natural gas consumption. In China, UGS is primarily achieved through conversion of abandoned gas reservoirs. Radial jet drilling (RJD) is an effective technology for secondary development of depleted reservoirs. The multi orifice nozzle is a critical component for efficient rock breaking and gas production. Swirling multiorifice nozzle has fewer backward orifices, resulting in less energy loss and a larger discharge coefficient. It penetrates near-well contamination zones, enhances single-well control area, and improves reservoir pressure distribution. The forward orifice generates a forward-velocity jet that breaks the formation, creating a radial borehole. The backward orifice produces a backward-velocity jet that creates reverse thrust.

(4) Investigation of the factors affecting the self-propelled force in a multi-orifice nozzle using a novel simulation method**Energy Science And Engineering, 25 May 2020, Yumei Li, Tao Zhang**

- Utilizes ANSYS-CFX 3D flow field simulation model to study the self-propelled force of a multi-orifice nozzle. Results show slight increase in self-propelled force with increasing angle of forward orifice and decrease with increasing backward orifice. Self-propelled forces align with calculation methods with an average accuracy of 95.82%. Increase in micro-hole diameter reduces self-propelled force and increases with inlet flow rate. Research improves multi-orifice nozzle performance and provides theoretical guidance for hydraulic radial jet drilling process. The technology allows a 90° turn from vertical to horizontal after casing opening. Drilling depth significantly impacts productivity. When drilling depth exceeds 15m, productivity ratio is 2-3 times higher than conventional perforation.

(5) Study on Water Jet Characteristics of Square Nozzle Based on CFD and Particle Image Velocimetry**Published: 12 November 2022, Zhuo Fu, Kun Li, Yongjun Pang, Liyong Ma**

- Through nozzle research, some scholars have found that non-circular nozzles are more effective than standard circular nozzles in some properties, such as uniform water distribution, jet cohesion, and stronger impact force. Comparing the round, regular triangle, and square nozzle, Liu et al concluded that the square nozzle has a faster jet speed, a relatively longer constant velocity core, and better cohesion. Hence, it is more suitable for jet-breaking operations under submerged conditions. He demonstrated that the square nozzle has higher transmission efficiency and a better stream concentration; therefore, the water jet via the square nozzle

has a more noticeable erosion effect on the depth and volume. The above studies mostly focused on the influence of different outlet facets on the nozzle jet performance, failing to cover the effects of the inner shape change of a noncircular nozzle on the external flow field of the jet nozzle. This study exposes what happens on the external flow field of the jet nozzle with changes in the two main structural parameters, corroborated by a PIV experiment.

(6) Structural optimization design of ice abrasive water jet nozzle based on multi-objective algorithm
Flow Measurement and Instrumentation

Volume 97, July 2024, 102586, Ying Liu, Xiaoyang Chen, Jun Zhang, Lele Feng, Huiwen Liu,

- The ice abrasive water jet (IAWJ) was optimized to improve cleaning efficiency. The design variables included the nozzle's structure and flow process parameters. The optimization objectives were maximum wall static pressure, outlet velocity, and wash width. 50 sets of sample capacity were designed using the Optimal Latin Hypercube Sampling (OLHS) method. MATLAB fitted parameter functions for the three objectives. The Competitive Mechanism Multi-Objective Particle Swarm Optimizer (CMOPSO) algorithm was used to improve the cleaning effect. Inlet pressure and outlet diameter were critical factors influencing the cleaning effect. The optimized nozzle produced a 4.5% higher maximum wall static pressure and a 10% higher cleaning effect than the ordinary cosine nozzle. The optimized nozzle serves as a reference for cleaning machine nozzle structure design.

(7) Experimental studies of the wear rate of jet-forming nozzles when implementing water jet technologies

Transportation Research Procedia

Volume 57, 2021, Pages 200-209, Konstantin Golovin, Aleksander Pushkarev, Anastasia Kovaleva

- Water jet cutting technology was introduced in the oil industry of Canada and the United States for drilling oil wells. Water mixed with abrasive particles was used for cutting materials with various properties. However, due to rapid wear of water jet equipment, it was decided to stop using this technology. High-speed jets of liquid are comparable to modern cutting machines and can process complex profiled items with minimal material loss due to their small cutting width. To avoid gaseous combustion products and material deformation, tools must have a small reactive force and low temperature (up to 90°C). Water jet cutting can be used with various materials, including metals, plastics, glass, and natural stone slabs. A unique method for water jet processing surfaces with arbitrary shapes is currently being applied, allowing cleaning from contaminants and coatings without damaging the base. This method involves mixing a low-pressure slurry jet with a high-pressure air jet, accelerating the mixture to the sound speed.

(8) Experimental and numerical investigation on thermochemical erosion and mechanical erosion of carbon-based nozzles in hybrid rocket motors

Aerospace Science and Technology

Article· Volume 148, May 2024, 109097, Xiangyu Meng, Hui Tian, Xianzhu Jiang

- This paper investigates the thermochemical and mechanical erosion mechanism of carbon-based nozzles in hybrid rocket motors with aluminum metallized fuel. A firing test is conducted using 95% hydrogen peroxide and hydroxyl-terminated polybutadiene based fuel with aluminum particles. Experimental results show that many metal particles are ejected from the nozzle, and aluminum oxide deposits heavily on the nozzle inner surface. A method of numerical calculation coupled with two-phase flow, combustion of aluminum metallized fuel, thermochemical ablation reactions, and mechanical erosion is established. Simulation results show that with increasing aluminum content, nozzle wall pressure increases, while the mass fraction of H₂O, CO₂, OH, and O declines. The nozzle wall temperature and thermochemical erosion rate increase first and then reduce as aluminum content increases. Mechanical erosion is mainly distributed in the convergent section and increases with aluminum content. The maximum mechanical and thermochemical erosion rates are 0.09185 mm/s and 0.0976 mm/s, respectively.

(9) Influences of geometry configurations on the performance of micro-nozzles

Acta Astronautica

Article· Volume 215, February 2024, Pages 618-630, Xinjie Li, Guobiao Cai, Junya Yuan

- Micro-nozzles are crucial in applications like aerospace and microelectronic systems. Due to their small size, they can experience both continuum and rarefied flow. This research investigates the optimal geometry configuration of micro-nozzles to achieve comprehensive performance, size, and background pressure compensation. Using classical computational fluid dynamics and direct simulation Monte Carlo methods, the study finds that micro-nozzle performance is influenced by the interplay between flow expansion and viscous

loss induced by the subsonic layer next to the micro-nozzle wall. The results show that micro-nozzle performance improves with increasing expansion ratio in slip and continuum flow regimes but decreases in the transition flow regime. The axisymmetric micro-nozzle outperforms the linear micro-nozzle in terms of performance and size, making it the recommended choice for practical applications. Plugs designed at the throat decrease performance but increase stability under diverse background pressures. This study offers valuable insights for designing high-efficiency micro-nozzles for applications like nanosats and MEMS heat dissipation units.

(10) Optimal shape design of printing nozzles for extrusion-based additive manufacturing
Additive Manufacturing

Volume 84, 25 March 2024, 104130, Tomás Schuller, Maziyar Jalaal, Paola Fanzio, Francisco J.

- The optimal design seeks the best possible solution(s) for a mechanical structure, device, or system, satisfying a series of requirements and leading to the best performance. In this work, optimized nozzle shapes have been designed for a wide range of polymer melts to be used in extrusion-based additive manufacturing, which aims to minimize pressure drop and allow greater flow control at large extrusion velocities. In the optimization process, variable coordinates for the nozzle's contraction section are defined, the objective function is selected, and the optimization algorithm is guided within manufacturing constraints. Comparisons of flow-type and streamline plots reveal that the nozzle shape significantly influences flow patterns. Finally, experimental validation of the nozzle performance assessed the actual printing flow, the extrusion force and the overall print control.

(11) Optical patterning of a multi-orifice spray nozzle
Atomization and Sprays

Article·Volume 15, Issue 6, 2005, pp. 687-698, Jongmook Lim, Yudaya R. Sivathanu

- A multi-orifice nozzle was patterned using an extinction tomography-based optical patterner, obtaining path-integrated transmittances from a six-orifice nozzle at 1000 Hz. The path-integrated transmittances were deconvoluted using the maximum likelihood estimation method and a novel grid scheme. The optical patterner's limitations in size and optical arrangement resulted in path-integrated extinction measurements at six view angles. However, a new grid scheme increased angular resolution by compromising radial resolution, resulting in a more uniform segment size distribution and reducing deconvolution errors. The deconvolution method, combined with the new grid scheme, successfully resolved the spatial distribution of surface area per unit volume of drops in a horizontal plane within the spray.

(12) Experimental and numerical studies on the performance of supersonic multi-nozzle ejector
Applied Thermal Engineering, Applied Thermal Engineering

Volume 242, 1 April 2024, 122409, Zhiyan Li, Wanwu Xu, Tao Liang, Wei Ye

- Study focuses on two supersonic multi-nozzle ejectors (single nozzle and four nozzles). Four-nozzle ejector requires higher starting pressure due to shock and friction loss. Priority is given to four-nozzle ejector when compression ratio exceeds 8 or entrainment ratio drops below 0.068. Four-nozzle ejector has shorter non-mixing length than single-nozzle ejector. Supersonic ejectors, also known as jet pumps, operate by pumping and compressing high-pressure flow to create a vacuum environment. The number of primary nozzles enhances ejector performance, leading to the development of the multi-nozzle ejector (MNE). MNE design features an increased shear area between the primary and secondary flows, promoting efficient mixing within a shorter mixing chamber. MNEs have been used in various applications, including autonomous mobile laser systems, aero-engine oil cooling systems, and hydrogen recirculation in proton exchange membrane fuel cell systems. Numerous studies have been conducted to analyze the performance of MNEs, revealing relationships between nozzle numbers, mixing chamber, nozzle spacing ratio, and diffuser angle.

III. OBJECTIVES

- To design a hydro jetting nozzle capable of efficiently removing various types of contaminants from surfaces while minimizing water consumption and environmental impact.
- To conduct comprehensive computational fluid dynamics (CFD) analysis to simulate and optimize the internal flow characteristics of the nozzle, ensuring optimal performance and efficiency in different operating conditions.
- To develop practical recommendations and guidelines for the design, implementation, and maintenance of hydro jetting systems, aiming to provide valuable insights for industries and municipalities seeking to improve their cleaning processes.

IV. METHODOLOGY

V. DESIGN CONSIDERATION

1. Design Parameters:

1. Desired Flow Rate (Q): 10 gallons per minute (GPM) = 0.63 liters per second (L/s)
2. Desired Pressure (P): 3000 pounds per square inch (PSI) = 20700 kilopascals (kPa)
3. Nozzle diameter (D): To be determined

Calculation Steps:

Step 1: Convert units to consistent system (eg., SI units).

- Convert GPM to L/s: $Q = 0.63\text{L/s}$
- Convert Psi to kPa: $P = 20700\text{kPa}$

Step 2: Use the following equation to calculate the orifice area (A):

$$A = \frac{Q}{C_d \sqrt{P}}$$

Where C_d is the discharge coefficient (typically around 0.95 for well- designed nozzles).

Let's assume $C_d = 0.95$:

$$A = \frac{0.63}{0.95 \times \sqrt{20700}}$$

$$A = \frac{0.63}{0.95 \times 144}$$

$$A = \frac{0.63}{136.8}$$

$$A = 0.0046 \text{ m}^2$$

Step 3: Calculate the nozzle diameter (D) using the orifice area (A):

$$A = \frac{\pi d^2}{4}$$

$$D^2 = \frac{4A}{\pi}$$

$$D = \sqrt{\frac{4A}{\pi}}$$

$$D \approx \sqrt{\frac{4 \times 0.0046}{\pi}}$$

$$D \approx \sqrt{0.0012}$$

$$D \approx 0.0346 \text{ m}$$

Conclusion:

- The calculated nozzle diameter (D) is approximately 0.0346 m or 34.6 mm

This is a simplified example, and actual nozzle design may involve additional factors, such as the specific type of nozzle, material considerations, and adjustments based on practical experience. It is crucial to consult with experienced engineers and nozzle manufacturers for a detailed and accurate design for a specific hydrojetting application.

2. Design Parameters:

1. Desired Flow rate (Q): 10 GPM = 0.63 L/s
2. Desired Pressure (P): 3000 PSI = 20700 kPa
3. Discharge Coefficient (C_d): 0.95

Additional Factors:

1. Material considerations:

Choose a material that can withstand high-pressure water and is resistant to corrosion, common materials include stainless steel or hardened alloys.

2. Nozzle Geometry:

Consider the nozzle shape and angle based on the application requirements.

For example, a rotating nozzle may provide a more even cleaning pattern.

3. Practical Constraints:

Consider practical limitations such as manufacturing capabilities, cost constraints, and ease of maintenance.

Calculation Steps:

Step 1 : Orifice Area (A):

$$A = \frac{Q}{C_d \sqrt{P}}$$

$$A = \frac{0.63}{0.95 \times \sqrt{20700}}$$

$$A \approx 0.0046 \text{ m}^2$$

Step 2 : Nozzle diameter (D):

$$D = \sqrt{\frac{4A}{\pi}}$$

$$D \approx \sqrt{\frac{4 \times 0.0046}{\pi}}$$

$$D \approx 0.0682 \text{ m}$$

Conclusion:

- The calculated nozzle diameter (D) is approximately 0.0682 m or 68.2 mm.
- Choose a practical diameter based on available nozzle sizes.

Practical Considerations:

- Confirm that the selected material is suitable for the application.
- Choose a commercially available nozzle size that is close to the calculated size.
- Consider the specific geometry of the nozzle, taking into account the desired spray pattern and angle.

This design provides a more realistic approach by considering additional factors, but it's important to collaborate with experienced engineers and manufacturers for a detailed and application-specific hydrojetting nozzle design.

For 2mm diameter

Q-Discharge

V-Velocity

A-Area of cross section

$$Q = V \cdot A$$

$$V = \frac{Q}{A}$$

$$Q = 100 \text{ LPM} = 0.001667 \frac{\text{m}^3}{\text{sec}}$$

$$d_{\text{out}} = 2 \text{ mm}$$

$$d_{\text{in}} = 22 \text{ mm}$$

$$A = \frac{\pi d^2}{4} = \frac{\pi (2 \times 10^{-3})^2}{4} = 3.1416 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^2$$

$$V_{\text{out}} = \frac{0.001667}{3.1416 \times 10^{-6}} = 530.6 \text{ m/s}$$

$$V_{\text{in}} = \frac{0.001667}{1.727 \times 10^{-5}} = 4.38 \text{ m/s}$$

Boyle's Law states that pressure is inversely related to volume. This means that when pressure is increased, volume is decreased

Boyle's Law states that when temperature is constant:

$$P_1 \cdot V_1 = P_2 \cdot V_2$$

P_1 -Pressure at inlet (bar) = 5 bar

P_2 -Pressure at outlet (bar) =?

V_1 -Velocity at inlet (m/s) =4.38 m/s

V_2 -Velocity at outlet (m/s) = 530.6 m/s

$$P_2 = \frac{P_1 \cdot V_1}{V_2} \text{ bar}$$

$$P_2 = \frac{5 \times 4.38}{530.6} = 0.041 \text{ bar}$$

Bernoulli's principle states that an increase in the speed of a fluid occurs simultaneously with a decrease in pressure or a decrease in the fluid's potential energy.

VI. Design of Nozzle

Fig. 1 Design of multi orifice nozzle using catia software

VII. Meshing

For 2mm diameter

Fig. 2 Inlet Velocity

Fig. 3 Outlet Velocity

Fig. 4 Inlet Pressure

Fig. 5 Outlet Pressure

Fig. 6 Meshing of 2mm orifice diameter nozzle

VIII. Analysis using Ansys Software

Analysis of 2mm orifice diameter nozzle

Fig .7 Pressure Analysis along x direction

Fig .8 Pressure Analysis along z direction

Fig .9 Velocity Analysis along x direction

Fig .10 Velocity Analysis along z direction

Fig .11 Velocity Analysis along x direction

Fig .12 Velocity Analysis along z direction

Fig .13 Velocity Analysis along y direction

Fig .14 Velocity Analysis along y direction
For 2.25mm diameter

Analysis of 2.25mm orifice diameter nozzle

Fig .15 Velocity Analysis along x direction

Fig .16 Velocity Analysis along y direction

Fig .17 Velocity Analysis along z direction

Fig .18 Velocity Analysis along x direction

Fig .19 Velocity Analysis along y direction

Fig .20 Velocity Analysis along z direction

Fig .21 Pressure Analysis along x direction

Fig .22 Pressure Analysis along y direction

Fig .23 Pressure Analysis along z direction

IX. Residual chart

Fig. 30 Pressure and velocity at centre of nozzle

At-inlet

Fig. 31 Pressure and velocity at inlet of nozzle

At-outlet

Fig. 32 Pressure and velocity at outlet of nozzle

X. CONCLUSION

- Through careful analysis and experimentation, we have explored the multifaceted facets of hydro jetting technology; understand its potential applications and optimizing its performance.
- By employing computational simulations and experimental validations, we have been able to refine the design parameters of the nozzle, enhancing its efficiency and efficacy in various industrial and commercial settings.
- By fine-tuning these parameters, we can tailor the hydro jetting process to specific requirements, whether it be surface cleaning, debris removal, or industrial cutting applications.

XI. REFERENCES

- [1] Oleg Urazmetov, "Investigation of the flow phenomena in high-pressure water jet nozzles", *Chemical Engineering Research And design*, Volume 165, Pages 320-332, January 2021
- [2] Chuanfu Shao, "Experimental and numerical investigation of abrasive water jet nozzle Erosion", *Powder Technology*, Volume 430, 1 December 2023, 119031
- [3] Li Jingbin, "Rock breaking characteristics of the self-rotating multi-orifices nozzle applied to coalbed methane radial jet drilling", *International Journal of Rock Mechanics and Mining Sciences*, *International Journal of Rock Mechanics and Mining Sciences*, Volume 136, December 2020, 104483
- [4] Qinghong Zhang, "Research on Flow Field Characteristics in Water Jet Nozzle and Surface Damage Caused by Target Impact", *Ocean and Hydropower*, 25 July 2022
- [5] Lihuanchen, "Design and Optimization of High-Pressure Water Jet for Coal Breaking and Punching Nozzle Considering Structural Parameter Interaction", *Optimization and Flow Charecteristics in Advanced Fluid Machinery*, 14 January 2022
- [6] Famu Huang , "Study on Energy Conversion Efficiency and Structure Optimization of the Multi orifices Nozzle for Radial Jet Drilling", *Geofluids*, Volume 2023 | Article ID 5517260 | 25 May 2023
- [7] Bozider Sarler, "Alternative Geometric Arrangements of the Nozzle Outlet Orifice for Liquid Micro-Jet Focusing in Gas Dynamic Virtual Nozzles", *Surface-Tension-Driven Flows for Shaping and Fragmenting Matter on the Submillimeter Scale*, 23 March 2021
- [8] Yumei Li, "Investigation of the factors affecting the self-propelled force in a multi-orifice nozzle using a novel simulation method", *Energy Science And Engineering*, 25 May 2020
- [9] Zhiyan Li, "Experimental and numerical studies on the performance of supersonic multi-nozzle ejector", *Applied Thermal Engineering*, *Applied Thermal Engineering*, Volume 242, 1 April 2024, 122409
- [10] Jingbin Li, Gensheng Li, "The self-propelled force model of a multi-orifice nozzle for radial jet drilling", *Journal of Natural Gas Science and Engineering*, Volume 24, Pages 441-448, May 2015
- [11] Nicolae MEDAN, "Evaluation of Nozzle Coefficients for Water Jet Used in Sewer Cleaning", *Article · September 2016*
- [12] Razali Abidin, "Design and Simulation of Nozzle for Pure Water Jet Portable Cutting Tool", *International Journal of Innovative Technology and Exploring Engineering (IJITEE)*, Volume-8 Issue-12S2, October 2019
- [13] Zhuo Fu "Study on Water Jet Characteristics of Square Nozzle Based on CFD and Particle Image Velocimetry", *Published: 12 November 2022*
- [14] Qijia Yang, "Impact of Laval nozzle structure on the flow characteristics of supersonic gas-solid two-phase flow", *Powder Technology*, Volume 439, 15 April 2024, 119657
- [15] Theodore Gabor "Numerical studies on cold spray gas dynamics and powder flow in circular and rectangular nozzles", *Journal of Manufacturing Processes*, Volume 114, 30 March 2024, Pages 232-246
- [16] Yi Niu, "Experimental investigation of rectangular nozzle aspect ratio effects on high-pressure helium leakage characteristics", *Journal of Loss Prevention in the Process Industries*, Volume 89, July 2024, 105306
- [17] Meiyibo Zhou, "Improving the cleaning uniformity of rectangular flat pleated filter with pulse-jet airflow by the new type of intensive injection nozzle", *Powder Technology*, Volume 439, 15 April 2024, 119697
- [18] Ying Liu, "Structural optimization design of ice abrasive water jet nozzle based on multi-objective algorithm", *Flow Measurement and Instrumentation*, Volume 97, July 2024, 102586
- [19] Konstantin Golovin, "Experimental studies of the wear rate of jet-forming nozzles when implementing water jet technologies", *Transportation Research Procedia*, Volume 57, 2021, Pages 200-209
- [20] Jinjin Wang, "Effect of nozzle width on droplet formation in wedge-shaped step-emulsification microchannel devices", *Colloids and Surfaces A: Physicochemical and Engineering Aspects*, Volume 691, 20 June 2024, 133879
- [21] Junfeng Wang, "Precise control of atomization initial stage to address nozzle clogging issue in the vacuum induction-melting gas atomization process", *Journal of Materials Research and Technology*, Volume 30, May–June 2024, Pages 1505-1517
- [22] Yong Wang, "Multi-objective aerodynamic optimization of expansion–deflection nozzle based on B-spline curves", *Aerospace Science and Technology*, Volume 147, April 2024, 109016
- [23] Xue Jiang, "Equivalent notional nozzle model for high nozzle pressure ratio leakage of petrochemical high-pressure facility", *Energy*, Volume 295, 15 May 2024, 131027
- [24] Chuang Li, "Heat transfer characteristics of water jet impingement on high-temperature steel plate by angular nozzle", *International Communications in Heat and Mass Transfer*, Volume 151, February 2024, 107243

- [25] Xiangyu Meng, “Experimental and numerical investigation on thermochemical erosion and mechanical erosion of carbon-based nozzles in hybrid rocket motors”, *Aerospace Science and Technology*, Volume 148, May 2024, 109097
- [26] Zhuqiang Yang, “Study on flow heat transfer and strength characteristics of a double-layer thin-wall active cooling nozzle”, *Applied Thermal Engineering*, Volume 243, 15 April 2024, 122586
- [27] Xinjie Li, “Influences of geometry configurations on the performance of micro-nozzles”, *Acta Astronautica*, Volume 215, February 2024, Pages 618-630
- [28] Tomás Schuller, “Optimal shape design of printing nozzles for extrusion-based additive manufacturing”, *Additive Manufacturing*, Volume 84, 25 March 2024, 104130
- [29] Jongmook Lim, “Optical patterning of a multi-orifice spray nozzle”, *Atomization and Sprays*, Volume 15, Issue 6, 2005, pp. 687-698
- [30] Buxian XU, “Dynamic characteristics and application of dual throat fluidic thrust vectoring nozzle”, *Chinese Journal of Aeronautics*, 15 April 2024